

DEGREE PROJECT IN ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING,
SECOND CYCLE, 30 CREDITS
STOCKHOLM, SWEDEN 2018

Degradation of Microplastic Residuals in Water by Visible Light Photocatalysis

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TRITA TRITA-ABE-MBT-18493

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This master thesis is a part of the current research of FNM group, Department of Applied physics, KTH on ‘Cleaning marine litter by developing and applying innovative methods in European seas (CLAIM)’ - EU horizon 2020 project with an aim to targeting the prevention of visible and invisible marine litter.

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Degree Project Master Level
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Reference should be written as: Tofa, T., (2018) “Degradation of microplastic residuals in water by visible light photocatalysis”.

TRITA-ABE-MBT 18493

Summary in Swedish

Föroreningar på grund av mikroplaster (MP) har nyligen erkänts som ett hot mot biosfären inklusive människor på grund av dess stora utspridning, ihärdighet och extremt små bitar. Avloppsreningsverk har identifierats som en viktig av mikroplastik föroreningskälla i vattenlevande system. Inga tidigare studier har rapporterat nedbrytande av den här framväxande föroreningen i vatten. Denna studie fokuserar på neobrytning av MP (närmare bestämt polyetylen med låg täthet, LDPE) i fast form med hjälp av en heterogen fotokatalyserad process under synligt ljus genom att modifiera fotokatalysatorer bestående av zinkoxidnanopelare (ZnO NR) och platinapartiklar deponerade på ZnO NR (PtNPs-ZnONR). Zinkoxid är en metalloxidhalvledare det där accelerera reaktioner utan att förbrukas i fotodegraderingprocessen.

Fotokatalysatorerna bedömdes enligt standardprotokoll (ISP 10678: 2010), och karakteriserades genom med SEM, EDX och optiska spektroskopier (UV-VIS och PL). Storleken och kvantiteten av platina nanopartiklar deponerade på ZnO nanopelare påverkar hur effektiv fotokatalysen är. En optimal deponeringstid (10 min) för Pt-NPs på ZnO NRs fastställdes, vilket ökade nedbrytningshastigheten med ungefär 38 % under UV ljus och 16,5 % under synligt ljus genom att förbättra både separations processen för elektron-hål par och absorberingen av synligt ljus. Hydroxylradikaler är de huvudsakliga bidragarna till fotodegraderingpr processen som testades genom att tillföra isopropanol (IP) i MB- lösning (IP konsumerar OH-radikaler).

50 mikroner tjock kommersiell LDPE-plastik folie användes i studien. Fotokatalyserad degradering bekräftades med FTIR-spektroskopi, dynamisk mekaniks analys (DMA), optisk mikroskopi och elektronmikroskopi. När LDPE-filmer med Pt-ZnO bestrålades så visade det sig att degradingen hände snabbare än med endast ZnO av liknande koncentration som visade bildandet av ett stort antal skrynklor, sprickor och hål över hela filmen. Förändring av funktionella grupper med låg molekylvikt som hydroperoxider, peroxider, karbonyl och vinyl grupper observerades i FTIR-spektra av LDPE-film under fotokatalys. Den dynamiska mekaniska analysen indikerade ökad styvhet och försprödning av bestrålade LDPE-filmer i nära fotokatalysatorer. Således ger det närvarande arbetet en ny inblick om modifierade katalysatorer för degradingen av mikroplasterna i vatten genom att använda synligt ljus.

Abstract

Microplastic (MP) pollution has recently been recognized as a threat to the biosphere including humans due to its widespread distribution, persistent nature and infinitesimal size. This study focused on the solid phase degradation of microplastic residues (particularly low density polyethylene, LDPE) in water through heterogeneous photocatalysis process by designed photocatalysts of zinc oxide nanorods (ZnO NRs) and platinum nanoparticles deposited on zinc oxide nanorods (Pt NPs-ZnO NRs) under visible light irradiation. These photocatalysts were assessed following standard protocol (ISP 10678: 2010), and characterized using SEM, EDX and optical spectroscopies (UV-VIS and PL). Deposition of Pt-NPs on ZnO NRs for certain minutes has been found optimum that enhanced the photodegradation process about 38% under UV irradiation and 16.5% under visible light irradiation by improving of both electrons-holes pair separation process and visible light absorption. Photocatalytic degradation of LDPE films was confirmed by FTIR spectroscopy, dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA), optical and electron microscopes. When LDPE film irradiated in presence of Pt-ZnO, degradation was found quicker than ZnO alone of similar concentration which exhibited formation of a large number of wrinkles, cracks and cavities on the film surface. Dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) test indicated stiffness and embrittlement of exposed LDPE films in presence of photocatalysts. Thus, the present work provides a new insight about modified catalysts for the degradation of microplastics in water using visible light.

Keywords

Microplastics, Low density Polyethylene (LDPE), Heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation, Zinc oxide nanorods, Visible light.

Acknowledgements

The author acknowledges the blessings of Almighty Allah, The Beneficent, and The Merciful for enabling to complete the study successfully and peacefully.

First, I would like to express my heartiest gratitude to my supervisor, Prof. Dr. Joydeep Dutta, who has been very encouraging and supportive throughout the entire thesis period. His guidance, motivation and counseling gave me incentive to improve individual research capability while executing the research. I consider myself blessed to be able to work under his supervision.

Likewise, I express my sincere gratitude to Prof. Dr. Elzbieta Plaza, Department of sustainable development, environmental science and engineering (SEED), KTH for refereeing and trusting on my competency and also agreeing to be the examiner of the thesis.

It has been a privilege to be a part of the Division of Functional Materials (FNM) and to work in the chemistry lab where I have learnt semiconductor designs along with nano-characterization tools. The author likes to thank Dr. Abdusalam Uheida and Dr. Fei Ye for their enormous support during experimentation and characterizations.

Appreciation is given to Karthik Laxman, Postdoctoral student, for his discussion and insightful suggestions. My time in FNM has allowed me to meet new friends, from whom I got continuous inspiration, love, care and support. Special thanks to Axel Strömberg (Ph.D. candidate) for his contribution in translating summary into Swedish.

I am also thankful to Dr. Swarej Paul, PP Polymer AB for contribution to the test and cooperation with related information needed for this study.

Finally, I confer gratitude to my beloved parents, brothers and sister for their continuous prayer, patience and support throughout the period of study. Last, but not the least, I want to reckon the hardship, continual support and sacrifices made by my husband, Mohammad Rafiqul Islam.

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List of abbreviations and symbols

λ : Wavelength

ν : Frequency

gm: Gram

mol: Molarity

μm : micro meter

nm: nano-meter

mm: mili meter

CB: Conduction band

CI: Carbonyl index

DW: Distilled water

DMA: Dynamic mechanical analyser

e^- : Electron

EM: Electromagnetic spectrum

EDX: X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy

EtOH: Ethanol

FTIR: Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

h^+ : Hole

IR: Infrared

ISO: International organization for standardization

LDPE: Low density polyethylene

MB: Methylene blue

NHE: Normal hydrogen electrode

NR: Nanorod

NP: Nano-particle

$^*\text{OH}$: Hydroxyl radical

O_2^- : Superoxide anion

PE: Polyethylene

PL: Photoluminescence

Pt: Platinum

Pt-ZnO: platinum supported on zinc oxide

Redox: Reduction and oxidation

RG: Recombination- generation

RH: Polymer

SEM: Scanning Electron Microscope

SPR: Surface plasmon resonance

TiO₂: Titanium oxide

UV: Ultraviolet

UV-VIS: Ultraviolet- visible light spectroscopy

VB: Valence band

VI: Vinyl index

VIS: Visible light

WWTP: Wastewater treatment plant

ZnO: Zinc oxide

Introduction

Plastic pollution has been identified as a global concern owing to its persistence characteristic and ubiquitous distribution in the biosphere, endangering the whole ecosystem including animals and humans. The properties of being lightweight, durable, inexpensive have led to extensive use of plastics in everyday life (Laist, 1987). The global production of plastics in 2016 is estimated at over 330 million metric tons, an increment of 222 times from 1950 and exponentially growing. Merely a small quantity of the plastics is recovered, incinerated or recycled for further use. About 8.8% of plastic is recovered from municipal solid waste in the US whereas the situation is slightly better (30%) in Europe which means the rest of the products end up in landfills, waterways, drainage systems, wastewater plants, and the oceans (Statista 2018; Garcia and Robertson 2017).

The presence of tiny plastics in the ocean was first highlighted in the study of Carpenter and Smith during 1972. Some researchers indicated the ingestion of plastics by the seals and sea-birds. Likewise, the deaths of turtles were reported by the ingestion of plastic bags. All these reports and threats have been overlooked for a long time that lead to the immense propagation (over 150 million tons) of microplastic (MP) pollution (Bergmann et al. 2016).

Although there is no standard nomenclature for defining these tiny pieces, yet researchers termed it as 'microplastics (MPs)'. In general, it represents the plastic fragments having the size less than 5 mm. For better classification, it should be classified into nano ($< 1\mu$), micro (1mm - 1μ m), meso (1mm – 2.5cm), macro (2.5cm -1m), and mega (>1 m) particles (GESAMP 2015).

Current studies on MPs have confirmed the widespread distribution from the poles to the equator (Barnes et al. 2009). The fragments are already reported to be found both in the ocean surface and floor, estuaries and lakes together with marine and freshwater shorelines, subtidal sediments, and terrestrial ecosystem, including agricultural land (Bergmann, M. et al. 2016). MPs enter into the environment either directly from industrial abrasion, air blasting media, cosmetic products, textiles, and medicines as primary sources (Gregory 1996; Cole et al 2011) or by the breakdown of large particles by the action of environmental weathering, which is a secondary source. The fraction of primary and secondary microplastics is still unknown but it has been assumed to be the higher quantity of later one by Barnes et al. (2009). A recent study by Gouin et al. (2011) showed that a person uses 2.4 mg/day of PE microplastics as microbeads by using only fluid soap. Also, a single piece of cloth can generate about 1900 piece of plastic fibers per wash (Bergmann et al. 2016).

Larger items made of plastic materials that have obvious direct impact on ecosystems can be recovered and recycled or reduced its usage. The effects of the smaller fragment of plastics are somewhat unknown and also difficult to quantify (GESAMP 2015). These persistent species have the potentiality to transfer the harmful chemicals like persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and Endocrine-Disrupting Chemicals (EDC) into the body of species. Organisms can intake MPs as a food intentionally or unintentionally and several studies have confirmed presence in the intestinal region and gills of marine species like zooplankton, mussels, crabs, fishes, whales, and seabirds (GESAMP 2015; Fossi et al. 2012; Bergmann, et al.2016). As human beings consume marine species, eventual invasion of human body through food web, drinking water or by dust inhalation is a potential threat.

About 80% (Oceans Solutions Report, 2017) of consumed plastics eventually end up in the marine environment either through runoff of agricultural lands, landfills, or discharged effluents from industries, ships, and municipalities (Fig. 1). Careless littering, leaks, and mismanagement of waste are also responsible for such pollution. Some of the MPs enter by breaking down of litter in the land through the action of light, heat, oxygen, wave actions, and organisms.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of sources and possible pathways of MP contamination of water and land bodies (Veiga et al. 2016).

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) have been identified as one of the major potential sources of microplastics pollution in aquatic systems (Bergmann et al. 2016). Although the purpose of WWTPs is to remove harmful pollutants from waste water prior to its discharge, they mostly fail to trap these fragmented plastics using the conventional filtering systems. A large treatment plant in Glasgow was shown to discharge 260, 954 m³/d (population equivalent 650,000) effluent in nearby Clyde river containing 65 million MPs (Murphy et al 2016). Another study on 17 US WWTPs revealed a release of over 4 million microparticles per facility per day (Mason, S. et al 2016), while WWTP in Germany discharges on an average of 9×10^8 MPs/year (Dubai and Liebezeit 2013). Even with high trapping efficiency using membrane filter, some amount would be discharged along with effluent. This is because particles smaller than the filter mesh escapes and reaches to the water bodies through the effluents. Also, 99% (Magnusson and Noren 2014) of MPs retained in the sewage sludge is used as fertilizers on the land, which ultimately reach to the nearby aquatic system by surface runoff. Billions of MPs from all over the world are discharged every day into waterbodies which needs immediate attention and elimination.

These fragments of plastics in water bodies have only recently been acknowledged, and its sampling, identification, quantification, and degradation methods are still being developed (Blair et al. 2017). Natural degradation is impossible as some of these plastics are so persistent that it takes up to 600 years to degrade in water (European Commission-DG Environment 2011). Other approaches like recycling, reuse, incineration, and landfilling are generally used for the management of larger sized plastic wastes. One of few ways of removing MPs from water is to use of membrane (finer mesh) bioreactor (Beljanski et al. 2016). Such technology is expensive, gets easily clogged, energy consuming, and is still unable to ensure complete removal. Also, biodegradation of MPs using different microorganisms like bacteria, fungus is expensive, time-consuming, and requires special conditions for degradation. The applications of heterogeneous photocatalysis in water and wastewater treatment have proven to be successful where Limited studies showed that photo-oxidation using nanocatalyst can degrade plastics with a little amount of by-products, is by far the most promising and cleaning method. However, there has been no study to the best of our knowledge, on the solid-phase degradation of MPs in water using a nanoscale photocatalyst. Photocatalysis induces redox reactions and $\cdot\text{OH}$ - radicals in presence of water oxidizes the polymer surfaces leading to the breaking down to lower molecular weight groups in the polymer chain, finally mineralizing to CO_2 and H_2O , similar to the advanced oxidation processes where additional chemicals are added to produce the hydroxyl radicals (Ali et al. 2016; Shang et al. 2003).

Advanced oxidation process (AOP) is well known for the degradation of pollutants from water and wastewater. Heterogeneous photocatalysis is one such AOP processes that have gained significant popularity in environmental applications since Fujishima and Honda succeeded in splitting water using UV light-induced TiO_2 photo-anode (Schiavello 1988). However, the interest in utilizing of semiconductors as catalysts has taken speed only since 1981 (Mills and Le Hunte 1997). A number of studies have been found on the use of nanoscale semiconductor as 'green' photocatalytic agents mainly for the removal of both organic and inorganic pollutant from water, wastewater. The Nanomaterials are of great interest in photocatalysis because of their unique properties that provide better catalytic activities. In addition, the key factor of nanomaterials is to have a high surface area to volume ratio which allows higher oxidation of pollutants than normal bulk material (Kumer et al 2009) whereas hexagonal nanorods offer higher surface area in comparison with the spherical nanoparticles (Baruah et al. 2010). Nano scale rods are crystalline in the structure which offers more longevity while using in removing pollutant from water or wastewater.

Zinc oxide (ZnO) has gained popularity as a photocatalytic agent, compared to other metal oxides as it is non-hazardous, eco-friendly, antibacterial agent, and efficient and is relatively easier tuning to absorb visible portion of solar spectra (Sakthivel et al. 2003; Qi et al. 2017). Zinc oxide has a wide band gap with a large excitation binding energy of 60 meV (Laxman et al. 2017) which makes it more efficient for photocatalysis.

In this dissertation we have focused on the photocatalytic degradation of polyethylene (PE) using visible light irradiation because of its versatile and extensive use in the world. In addition, the study of Talvitie et al. (2016) showed, the majority of spotted MPs are either polyester (76%) or polyethylene (19%). The general uses of PE are films in the packaging industries, grocery bags, detergent bottles, containers, microbeads in the facial and pipe for construction. It has been reported in the IHS Markit (2016) that the demand for PE will increase at a rate of 4.2% annually from 2016 to 2021 where Asia, America, and Europe will be the major consumer of PE. Thus, removing PE from wastewater sources are of interest to prevent further pollution of the planet.

Aim and objectives

Considering all the challenges discussed, the main aim of the study is to disintegrate MP residues in water using visible light photocatalysis processes. To achieve the aim, the following objectives were set:

1. Designing and synthesis of visible light active, efficient and stable photocatalysts of ZnO nanorods (NRs) and platinum nanoparticles sensitized ZnO NRs (Pt-ZnO)
 - Efficient utilization of sunlight
 - Controlling electron recombination-generation processes
 - Separation of electron-hole efficiently
2. Following International Standards Organization's (ISO) tests for photocatalyst evaluation.
3. Assessing the morphology, absorption, and optical characteristics of the photocatalysts including observation of the degradation mechanism and kinetics of the test dye pollutant, methylene blue (MB).
4. Comparing the effects of designed photocatalysts on the disintegration of low density polyethylene (LDPE).
5. Evaluating the morphological, chemical, and visco-elastic properties of LDPE.
6. Finally, understanding the possible mechanism of photocatalytic oxidation of LDPE.

Structure of the thesis

This study is presented in five chapters. The first of which is the general introduction.

Chapter two contains a brief theoretical background including selective reviews of the relevant literatures.

Chapter three describes the reagents, apparatus, chemical synthesis methods of photocatalysts and experimental design and procedures. Nanomaterial characterization techniques have also been included in this chapter.

Chapter four has been divided into two sections based on the experiments that were carried out during this dissertation. The first sections discuss the results obtained from degradation of MB using Pt supported ZnO NRs. PE degradation using the designed photocatalysts has been explained in the second section.

Finally, chapter five focuses on the summery of findings, uncertainties and recommendations for future work.

Theoretical Background and Literature Review

This chapter showcases the theoretical background of the research topic based on the recent advances reported in literature. The first part is about different types of polymers and its application,

degradation processes along with mechanism and influential factors. The second part explains regarding the fundamental of photocatalysis and catalysts.

Types and uses of polymers

There are various types and grades of natural and synthetic polymers available in the world. Non-biodegradable polymers are long lasting, and its toxicity can harm both terrestrial and aquatic biodiversity. Based on the origin of source, the conventional classification based is shown in fig. 2. They can also be categorized as amorphous or crystalline based on structure. Thermoplastic and thermostat are other types of classification as per the bonding between polymeric chains.

Figure 2: Conventional classification of polymers.

Plastic is one type of synthetic or semi-synthetic polymer. Among many different types of plastics, six of them are most available in the global market and are used in many fields such as packaging (35%), infrastructures (25%), automotive (17%), agriculture (8%), electrical and electronics, marine, etc. (GESAMP 2015). Table 1 shows the global demand for commonly used polymers, demands, and hazardous score. The hazardous score has been provided based on the properties of the monomers that are carcinogenic, mutagenic or both. Higher the ranking, higher is the vulnerability (Lithner et al. 2011)

Table 1: Common application of polymers and its health hazard (Plasticseurope.org. 2018; GESAMP 2015; Galloway 2015).

Polymer types	Demand (%)	Applications	Relative hazard score
Polyethylene, PE (HDPE, LDPE)	34.4	Plastic bag, storage containers, cars, housewares, linear.	11
Polypropylene, PP	24.2	Rope. Bottle caps, gear, strapping	1
Polystyrene, PS	7.3	Boxes, cups, utensils, containers	1628-30

Poly-vinyl chloride (PVC)	16.5	Film, pipe, containers	5001-10,000
Polyurethane (PUR)	7.5	Household paintings	7380-13844
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	7.7	Bottles, strapping	4
Polyamide	-	Fishing nets, ropes	63-50
Polyester	-	Textiles, boats	-

Polyethylene (PE)

Polyethylene ($-\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}_2-$)_n belongs to simple polyolefin group, is made of ethylene by the action of catalysts and initiator. Additives are also used to make it more stable and durable. PE is a semi-crystalline, lightweight thermoplastic that shows high resistivity to environment. This study focused on degradation of polyethylene because of its high demand and versatile use in our daily life.

PE can be commonly categories based on their densities: low density polyethylene (LDPE), high density polyethylene (HDPE), linear: Low density polyethylene (LLDPE) and ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMW). Higher the branches, lower will be the density (Yousif and Haddad 2013).

Properties

It is necessary to have a comprehensive idea about the physical, chemical and mechanical properties of PE to compare with the results after degradation. Several factors like molecular structure, copolymers, molecular weight, morphology and surrounding environment influence the properties of polyethylene. It exhibits good fatigue, strength, and thermal properties along with resistance to wear and tear. It is hydrophobic, airborne and can float easily. Table 2 shows a summary of the properties of different grades of PE.

Table 2: Properties of different grade PE.

Characteristics	LDPE	HDPE
Physical appearance	transparent	Transparent to opaque
Density	0.917-0.94	0.95
Crystallinity	35-70%	60-90%
Tensile strength (MPa)	10-17	20-35
Specific volume	1.10-1.08	1.06-1.04

Water absorption (%)	0.005-0.015	0.005-0.01
Ductile/fragile temperature (°C)	-70	-70
Melting Temperature (°C)	105-120	120-130
Solvent resistance	Soluble in some aromatics above 60 °C	Unaffected below 80 °C
UV resistance	Fair	poor

Polymer degradation

There have been a number of researches that studied the degradation of the polymer. Polymer degradation is an irreversible process, defined by the involvement of different chemical reactions that alters the properties of the polymer, and eventually results in chain breakage. Degradation starts at the surface and slowly penetrates into the deep. The process solely depends on the structure of the polymer and other factors such as heat, light, radiative ions, mechanical, biological and enzymatic actions (Yousif and Haddad 2013).

Photo-degradation

Photodegradation is a process of breaking of the polymeric chain by absorption of photons induced by the light source. Polymer undergoes both physical and chemical changes through this process. Therefore, activation energy (table 3) is of prime importance in photodegradation. Specific polymers absorb a certain wavelength at which they become activated when photo exposed (Hirt et al. 1961).

Table 3: Activation wavelength for typical polymers.

Polymer type	Activation wavelength maxima (nm)
Polyester	325
Polystyrene	318
Polyethylene	300
Polypropylene	310
Polyvinyl chloride	320
Polyvinyl acetate	280
Polycarbonate	295

In general, there are two proposed mechanisms for photocatalytic degradation. Photo-oxidation is the most effective and governing process in presence of air and sunlight.

Photo-oxidative degradation

When photodegradation occurs in presence of oxygen, the process is called photo-oxidative degradation. Due to oxidation of polymer, several products like hydroxyl, peroxide, carbonyl groups etc. having low molecular weights are formed along the chain.

Factors affecting the degradation process

The fundamental photodegradation process is affected by two major factors: external and internal. External factors include temperature changes, humidity/water, oxygen, energy radiation, microorganisms and their enzymes, different solvents (acids or bases), and external loading. The molecular structures of polymer, defects, morphology, additives, impurities, and chromophoric groups are the main internal factors. The existence of the chromophoric group is the pre-requisite for photodegradation. Chromophores act as a sensitizer which can shift the absorbed light into more visible region up to 260 nm (Yousif and Haddad 2013).

Photo-oxidative degradation mechanism of polymer

Polymer undergoes degradation when exposed to light, heat, humidity, air, and catalysts. The fundamental mechanism has not been revised since 1940 which mentioned four different steps in the degradation process: initiation of the degradation reaction, propagation, branching and termination.

Initiation starts with formation of alkyl radicals either by abstraction of hydrogen or by the session of C-C bond at the impure centers or weak links. The process can be initiated in three ways: by using direct UV, by means of photosensitizer, and catalyst. Peroxy radicals are formed in presence of oxygen and propagate along the polymer chain until to form hydroperoxides and alkoxy radicals. Further oxidation results in branching and chain scission with possible generation of oxygenated compounds. The process leads in the formation of low molecular compounds like carboxylic acids, esters, alcohols etc. and causes micro-cracks within the polymers. The polymer becomes colorless first, followed by tarnishing, yellowing or darkening at the end (Shang et al. 2003; Yousif and Haddad 2013). The general mechanism of photo-oxidative degradation scheme is showing below:

Step 1: Initiation:

Step 2: Chain Propagation:

Step 3: Chain Branching:

Step 4: Chain scission/Termination:

Advanced oxidation

Advanced Oxidation Processes are defined by the set of chemical reactions that helps in removing organic and inorganic pollutants from the waste water by oxidation. The main applications of AOPs in wastewater are in the area of reducing heavy metals, solvents, dyes, pesticides, etc. AOPs are classified into irradiation and non-irradiation processes based on light illumination. Most general techniques available are UV, photolytic technique, fenton process, photo-Fenton process, ozonation, photocatalysis, biodegradation and radiation-induced degradation as shown in fig. 3 (Hisaindee et al. 2013).

Figure 3: Various types of AOPs.

Oxidizing agents are the main species that are responsible for oxidation. Most commonly used oxidizing agents are chlorine, ozone, hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radicals, permanganate etc. Hydroxyl radical poses very high oxidation potential of 2.8eV after fluorine (Parsons 2005).

Photocatalysis process can produce oxygen-based radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$, $\text{O}_2\cdot^-$) easily from water and atmosphere which is more energy efficient in comparison to other methods. The radicals formed through the oxidizing agents, lead to chemical degradation and even mineralization of the pollutants.

Introduction to photocatalysis

Photocatalysis is a process of speeding up photoreaction in presence of catalysts whereas catalyst is defined as a substance that expedite the reaction rate without being used up in the process; thereby reducing the activation energy of the substance. Both light and catalysts are necessary for conducting photocatalysis reactions. This study is mainly concerned with heterogeneous photocatalysis as the catalysts can occur in different phase from reactants, readily regenerated and have long service life.

Selection of ZnO semiconductor as photocatalytic agent

There are a number of semiconductors which are used as a photocatalysts such as zinc oxide (ZnO), titanium oxide (TiO_2), stannous oxide (SnO), iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), tungsten oxide (WO_3), zinc sulfide (ZnS), cadmium sulfide (CdS) etc. These catalysts act as a sensitizer in presence of light especially visible or near UV. Bandgap versus the electrochemical potential of hydrogen and oxygen is shown in fig. 4 which is defined as the difference between the valence band and the conduction band. Also, band gap position relative to $\text{OH}^*/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of semiconductor is of vast importance to allow the generation of $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals (Fig. 4), a very high potential oxidizing agent (Bessegato et al., 2015). Both ZnO and TiO_2 can be used as potential photocatalytic agents. However, the major drawbacks of TiO_2 are the less absorption of visible light as the activation energy is 220 nm with nearly small absorption after 370 nm (Cabrera et al. 1996). In addition, this metal oxide has been classified as Group 2B carcinogenic to human by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (2010).

Figure 4: Band gap energy of common semiconductors (Wang et al. 2017).

ZnO is nontoxic, cheap, widely accessible, eco-friendly, and easy to synthesis. Recent studies have shown a better photocatalytic performance of ZnO than TiO₂ (Sakthivel et al. 2003). Also, ZnO absorbs a large fraction of the solar spectrum and demonstrates enhanced quantum efficiency than TiO₂ (Akyol et al. 2004). The major portion of the solar light spectrum is visible and defect states of ZnO allow visible light absorption.

Solar energy utilization

Light is the main source of energy that required for the activation of the catalysts. The photons can be generated either from external sources (mercury, UV or halogen bulb) or from sunlight. The external sources are expensive and non-renewable. But use of this sunlight as a source of photons can be beneficial in many ways. Solar energy is clean, sustainable and cheap solution for removing of pollutants from water and wastewater. Earth receives about 89000 terawatts of insolation and this radiation contains mainly 3-5% of UV, 47% of VIS, and IR (Bora and Mewada 2017). Only a small portion of UV light (Fig. 5) reaches the earth's surface that is why designing a visible light active photocatalyst has been one of the main purposes of the study.

Figure 5: Distribution of electro-magnetic spectrum (Es-so-database.com. 2018).

ZnO properties

ZnO nanorods are 1-D wurtzite crystal structure which has a hexagonal unit cell having lattice parameter, $c = 0.3296\text{nm}$ and lattice constant, $a = 0.52065\text{ nm}$ with c/a constant of 1.633 (Klingshirn et al. 2013). Each Zn ion is surrounded by four oxygen anions, creating a tetrahedron arrangement.

The whole structure constitutes by a number of planes placed alternately along the c axis. ZnO has polar surfaces where both top and bottoms are positively charged with Zn²⁺ ions. The side surfaces along the c axis have the equal distribution of O²⁻ and Zn²⁺ ions (Das and Ghosh 2013). Crystal planes are of great importance as it influences the physical and electrical properties of the semiconductor. A schematic representation of the structure is shown in fig. 6. This promising ZnO semiconductor is mainly of n-type and a summary of different properties of ZnO is provided in appendix.

Figure 6: Crystalline structure of ZnO (Theochem.ruhr-uni-bochum.de. 2018; Das and Ghosh 2013).

Defects in ZnO

Defects are common in all crystals that influence both electrical and optical properties of semiconductors. They can introduce different energy levels inside bandgaps. Crystal defects are classified as point, line, surface and volume defects. Point defects like vacancies, interstitial and antisites play an important role in controlling the conductivity of ZnO (Janotti and Van de Walle 2009). Most common defects are oxygen interstitial (O_i), oxygen vacancies (V_o), Zinc vacancies (V_{zn}), and Zn interstitials (Zn_i) (Tomlins et al. 2000). When number of atom is less in comparison to a perfect lattice structure is called vacancies. Interstitial defects occur when atoms occupy within crystal structure.

Heterogeneous photocatalysis mechanism

During photocatalysis, photons ($h\nu$) generated from light source excite the electrons in the valence band of ZnO. These excited electrons lifted up into the vacant conduction band, leaving holes in the valence band which creates an oxidizing environment where these holes take part in the degradation process of polyethylene. Under this condition, ZnO (h^+) accepts electrons from water or from atmosphere (moisture) producing hydroxyl radical ($*OH$) and hydrogen ion (H^+). Under reducing condition, electrons in the conduction band produces superoxide ($*O_2^-$) anion in the presence of air or dissolved oxygen (Qi et al. 2017; Baruah et al. 2010, Baruah et al. 2012). The degradation of PE depends on the number of holes generated by photons. The fundamental mechanism of photocatalysis has been depicted by the following fig. 7.

The overall reactions are given below:

Reaction in the ZnO surface due to photon is: $ZnO + \text{photon } (h\nu) \rightarrow ZnO (e^-) + ZnO (h^+)$

Oxidation and reactions are:

Figure 7: Photocatalysis mechanism of ZnO.

Enhancement of photocatalysis

The major drawback of using ZnO as a catalyst is the wide band gap that requires shorter wavelength to get activated. Also, the performance of photocatalysis depends on the generation of a number of electrons and holes upon excitation and their recombination process. It has been mentioned in the review of Qi et al. (2017) that different types of metals, nonmetals, plasmonic metals, carbon materials were used by many researchers to enhance the photocatalytic activity of ZnO, as shown in fig. 8.

The study of Sakthivela et al. (2004) reveals the deposition of metal on TiO₂ can circumvent the underlying limitations and help in accomplishing the major objective of this study. Pt NPs loaded on

TiO₂ offers higher photonic efficiency in comparison with Au/TiO₂ and Pd/TiO₂. Therefore, this research focused on depositing plasmonic NPs of Pt with ZnO NRs to modify the surface condition for enhancing the photocatalysis process by reducing the RG process and improving visible light absorption.

Figure 8: Different process of improving photocatalysts efficiency.

Methodology

This chapter presents the experimental details involved in this thesis work including materials and reagents, catalysts synthesis and design, test setup, characterization and degradation techniques (Fig.9).

Reagents

Reagents like Zinc acetate dihydrate [Zn(CH₃COO)₂, Sigma Aldrich, 99% purity, molecular weight: 219.5 gm/mol] Hexamethylenetetramine [Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Sigma Aldrich, 99% purity, molecular weight: 140.19 gm/mol], Zinc nitrate hexahydrate [C₆H₁₂N₄, Sigma Aldrich, 99% purity, molecular weight: 297.47], Potassium hexachloroplatinate [K₂PtCl₆, Sigma Aldrich, 99% purity, molecular weight: [485.99 g/mol], methylene blue [C₁₆H₁₈ClN₃S, Sigma Aldrich, 99%, molecular weight: 319.85 g/mol, anhydrous basis], Acetone (C₃H₆O, Sigma Aldrich, 99.5%), and Isopropanol (C₃H₈O,

Sigma Aldrich, 99.7%], Ethanol [C₂H₆O, Sigma Aldrich, 99.5%] were used in this work without further purification for the whole process. Commercial Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) film having 50 µm was used as test sample for the degradation purpose.

Experimental process and paradigm

Figure 9: Process flow chart of the study.

Design of semiconductor

One of the aims of this study is to design a visible light active photocatalysts to ensure efficient use of sunlight and reduce the recombination process. So, the catalytic properties of ZnO have been modified by adding a small amount of platinum (Pt). Their synthesis process in the laboratory has been discussed below.

Hydrothermal synthesis of ZnO-NRs

The hydrothermal synthesis method was used for the growth of ZnO NRs due to ease in synthesis process and it offers more defects over a few hours of hydrolysis which is beneficial for absorbing a visible portion of light. To deposit NR arrays on the microscopic glass substrate, a thin layer of zinc oxide particles is seeded first using Zinc acetate (ZnAc) (Zn(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O) solution. Then, an equimolar solution of Hexamethylenetetramine (HMT) (C₆H₁₂N₄) and Zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) was prepared as a growth solution. HMT has high water solubility and drives the whole deposition process. The chemical reactions are summarized in the following (Zhang et al. 2012, Baruah and Dutta 2009).

Figure 10: Process of hydrothermal growth of ZnO NRs on glass substrate.

This microscopic glass slides, were used as substrates, with dimensions of 2.5 cm X 7 cm after cleaning with soap and sonicated for 20 minutes, followed by thorough washing with distilled water (DI) and subsequently cleaned with Isopropanol and acetone, sequentially. Substrates were then dried at 90° C in an oven and stored in desiccators until further use.

Zinc oxide seed crystals were deposited on the glass slides by spraying 10 mM zinc acetate dihydrate solution at a rate of 1 mL/min from about 15cm height while the slide was placed on top of a hot plate, maintained at a temperature of 350 °C. A thin uniform layer of ZnO NPs can be visibly observed on the glass substrates. The seeded slides were then stored in an oven maintained at 90 °C until further use. Zinc oxide NR growth solution was prepared by dissolving hexamethylenetetramine and zinc nitrate hexahydrate of pre-determined concentrations in DI water individually and then mixed vigorously using a magnetic stirrer for preparing equimolar 500 ml solutions. Table 1 shows different growth solutions prepared during the course of this work (See appendix 1). Seeded glass substrates were placed on glass frames in a petri dish filled with the growth solution in a way that the seeded layer faced downward. After the growth of nanorods, the substrates were gently washed with DI water and then annealed in an atmospheric oven at 350 °C for 1 hour followed by storage in desiccators until further use. The whole process is showing has been illustrated in the fig. 10.

Preparation of supported platinum (Pt) nanoparticles on ZnO-NRs

The prepared ZnO substrate was exposed to a UV-C bulb for 30 minutes from a distance of 14 cm followed by submerging the substrates in 1mM Pt (IV) solution and exposed to UV-C light again for

5, 10, 15 and 20 minutes to enable photo-reduction of the platinum containing precursor (fig. 11 and 12c). 1 mM aqueous solution of potassium hexachloroplatinate (K_2PtCl_6) was prepared by dissolving 19.44 mg salt into 10 mL DI water with sonication for 20 minutes. 6.25 mL of this solution was mixed with 18.75 mL ethanol to obtain a 1 mM Pt (IV) solution, where ethanol serves the purpose to expedite the deposition process (Al-Alawi et al. 2016). Following platinum deposition on ZnO NRs, the substrates were annealed at 450°C for 1 hour to obtain platinum NPs on ZnO NRs. The whole process is shown in fig. 11 and 12.

Figure 11: Schematic representation of the experimental setup for photochemical reduction of Pt on ZnO-NRs using UV-C light.

Figure 12: Photochemical reduction of Pt on ZnO-NRs. a) Pt solution preparation, b) reduction under UV light, and c) deposited Pt on ZnO NRs.

Experimental design and setup

Two different experiments have been conducted in this study and the experimental setup is discussed hereunder. Initial photocatalytic degradation studies were conducted using a test dye; methylene blue (MB) followed by the degradation studies of polyethylene (PE) films.

Preparation of MB solution and test setup for Pt supported ZnO catalysts

Methylene blue (MB), $C_{16}H_{18}ClN_3S$ is a well-known dye that is used as a pollutant for assessing photocatalytic efficiency of semiconductors as prescribed by the international standards

organizations (ISO 10678; 2010), thus MB was utilized to evaluate the photocatalytic activities of the semiconductor as a standard (Mills et al. 2012). The degradation of MB was followed by measuring the optical absorption of the MB solution after photocatalytic treatment in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Figure 13: Experimental set up for the photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB).

A 10 μM MB solution was prepared by dissolving 0.32 mg of MB in 100 mL of water. Total 3 mL MB along with the samples of different catalysts (ZnO and Pt-ZnO), having a substrate size of 2.5 cm X 0.75 cm, were exposed to light. This particular experiment was carried out under both ultraviolet (UV) light and visible (VIS) light irradiation in order to investigate the enhancement to visible light photocatalysis especially of the platinum coated ZnO nanoparticles. The light source was kept right above the sample as described in section 3.2. The light intensity of the white light source was adjusted to produce between 70-80 Klux. Plastic cuvettes were used to carry out the evaluation of the photocatalysts.

Total six samples including a reference (without any catalyst) were prepared and each was dipped into MB solution. It was necessary to keep the samples in the dark prior to exposure to allow the adsorption. All the parameters except catalyst and light source were kept constant so that the results are compared in the study. Photocatalysis experiments were carried out for 90 minutes at room temperature. The experimental setup is shown by the fig. 13.

Photocatalysis set-up for LDPE degradation

A 50W Dichroic halogen lamp (maintaining 90° angle) and 100 W mercury vapor lamp from Ultra-Violet Products Ltd, model B-100Y (at an angle of 45 °) were used at a distance of 10 cm and 15 cm

as visible and UV light source, respectively. The uniformity of the light intensity all over the sample was measured using a light meter (Model ST-1300) active in the range of 200 to 50,000 lux and sensitive to the wavelength from 400 to 700 nm (silicon photodiode). A black box of size 35 cm x 22 cm x 33.5 cm was always used during the photocatalytic degradation process to avoid external light sources interfering during the actual measurements.

Figure 14: Experimental set up for the photocatalytic degradation of LDPE films.

Photocatalytic degradation of PE in water was carried out under visible light in the ambient by keeping the light source at a distance of 10 cm from the sample. A solid plastic film sample of size (1 cm x 1 cm) along with ZnO and ZnO-Pt NRs substrate was submerged into the petri dish which was filled with water. A round beaker, having an outer dimension of 15 cm x 7 cm, was filled with 700 mL of water every 12 hours to maintain a pH of 7.0. The bulb created some heat to evaporate the water at a rate of 15 ml/hr. In fig. 14, we present the experimental set-up for the polymer disintegration using photocatalysts. The temperature of the water was continuously monitored during the photocatalysis process and was always found to be lower than 40°C. Composite films were continuously irradiated for 175 hours. FTIR characterization of the polymer was performed in between after 50 hours or 75 hours interval depending on the availability.

Degradation characterization mechanism

There are large numbers of techniques that can be used for studying the polymer degradation. Based on the properties of the polymer, these techniques are broadly classified into three categories: chemical, mechanical, and topological. The available options and their uses are illustrated in the following fig. 15.

The visco-elasticity test was used for observing the mechanical strength of the polymer film samples. Tensile strength test could not be performed due to the size of the sample. Scanning Electron Microscope and Transmission Electron Microscopy provided morphological information of the materials. FTIR generated information about functional groups which qualitatively measures the breakdown of the polymer. UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to determine the degradation kinetics of MB. Optical properties of the coatings were measured through both UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopy. Detail of the characterization techniques have been discussed in the following section.

Figure 15: General techniques for characterization of degraded polymer (Kumer et al. 2009).

Morphological properties

Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) (FEG-SEM: Ultra 55, ZEISS) was used for the determination of surface topography, composition and size range of catalysts. It uses focused beams containing electrons to obtain images of samples at nano-scales. The beams only penetrate and interact within a specific volume. Samples were prepared by cutting into 0.5 cm x 0.5 cm size. Some of the samples were coated with a thin layer of gold to avoid charging related aberrations. The acceleration voltage of electrons was kept 3 KV whereas working distance was varied between 3 to 10 mm depending on the catalysts type.

X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)

EDS was used in the study as an analytical tool for the identification and quantification of element of samples. Each element showed characteristics peak and relative abundance when exposed to x-rays.

Optical microscope

The Leica (Model: DFC295, 12730469) digital microscope of 3.0-megapixel (2048 X 1536) resolution camera was used for observing the changes over the surface of the polyethylene.

Visco-elastic property

visco-elastic properties of the films through Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). Contrary to tensile testing, DMA measures the changes in the mechanical properties at a molecular level (visco-elastic properties) and it is also possible to investigate the mechanical properties as a Polyethylene is a semi-crystalline material having both elastic component (E') and viscous component (E''). Elastic component imitates by the elastic deformation of the polymeric chains arising from the amorphous and the crystalline part of the material whereas the viscous part arises from the movement of polymer segments (Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA): A beginner guide, 2018).

The measurement consists of adjusting some parameters like are temperature, frequency, and the amplitude for dynamic and static loads. The prestressed LDPE samples were exposed to a sinusoidal stress and the sinusoidal strain formed because of this stress is measured at different temperature. The test has DMA runs were performed between -20°C and $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$ at frequency of 1 Hz. Only elastic component (E') of the four irradiated LDPE samples were measured as a function of temperature. Storage modulus is the measure of determining the elastic behaviour of polymer (Dynamic Mechanical Analysis, 2014). It was calculated through

$$\text{Storage modulus, } E' = \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon} * \cos\beta$$

Where, σ = maximum stress, ϵ = maximum strain, and β = phase angle in radian between the dynamic stress and the dynamic strain in a visco-elastic material subjected to a sinusoidal oscillation.

Optical property

Photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL)

A photoluminescence spectrometer from PerkinElmer (LS 55: Fluorescence spectroscopy) was used for estimating optical emission (mainly the defect level emission) of ZnO coatings. Photo excitation of semiconductors occurs as a result of absorbing energy higher than band gap energy. When the excited electrons reach to their equilibrium states, the excess energy absorbed by the catalyst is released. The emitted light (arising from radiative recombination processes) is called photoluminescence which is the difference in energy between excited state and an equilibrium state. The main task for using PL for this study was to understand the energy levels of impurities and defects levels (like oxygen deficiency) in semiconductor.

Prepared catalysts, ZnO and Pt-ZnO were placed in the sample holder and the system was configured for the measurement. The excitation wavelength used was 320 nm, scan range was selected from 340 to 620 nm at a rate of 50 nm/min, and the slit size was kept 5. These values were kept constant to make comparable analysis in this study.

Other properties

UV-Vis spectroscopy

Absorption or reflectance spectrum of the substance was studied by UV-Vis spectroscopy of model PerkinElmer's LAMBDA-750 UV/Vis. Usually, the absorption value of sample was measured using 3 mL quartz cuvette. The system was calibrated before every measurement. In principle, when light (I_0) passes through a sample, the elements in the material absorb some light (I), and the remainder passes through.

UV-Vis spectroscopy was utilized to determine the degradation kinetics of MB and to understand the nanomaterial features. Effect of photocatalysts on MB degradation was observed through the absorption vs. wavelength curve. The degradation kinetics, the rate constant and % degradation was calculated using the Langmuir-Hinshelwood (Scuderi et al. 2016) equations.

$$\frac{C}{C_0} = e^{-kt}$$

$$\% \text{ degradation} = \frac{I_0 - I}{I_0} \times 100$$

Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR)

The percentage (%) transmittance or absorbance of infra-red ranges between 525 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} was measured using Thermo scientific: Nicolet is10 fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The FTIR spectra were obtained in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode by placing the solid polyethylene on the Zinc Selenide crystal window. Background spectrum was acquired out before collecting sample spectra. The scans were performed for 32 times. Baseline correction was also made for all the data.

Infra-red light from source passes through the sample and then transmitted light is detected by the detector. The light is absorbed by the functional group when their frequencies match. Different molecules in compounds have signature vibrational bands at specific wavenumbers which help to detect the functional group; thereby, follow the degradation of polyethylene materials, in our case.

Introduction to functional group

Figure 16: Vibration mode and band categories of FTIR (Wade 2003).

A functional group specifies a definite group of atoms or bonds within a molecule that is accountable for characteristic chemical reactions of that molecule. Bond vibrations are of three types: stretching, rocking, and bending (fig. 16). Depending on the relative IR intensities in the spectrum, they can also be classified as strong, medium and weak (Socrates 2001).

Photooxidation of polymers under light forms new functional groups which is reason to understand the evolution of functional groups order to predict the undergoing chemical reactions. Functional groups that are commonly observed in the FTIR have been summarized below in Table 4.

Table 4: Overview of organic functional groups of polymers.

Bond types	Groups	Structure	Type of vibration, Intensity	
Carbon– carbon bonds	Alkene	-C=C-	Stretching, strong	
	Carbon– oxygen bonds (carbonyl group)	Aldehydes		Stretch, Strong
		Ketones		
		Carboxylic Acids		
		Esters		
oxygen- hydrogen bonds	Alcohols		Strong, broadly stretched an H bonded; Stretch free	

Carbonyl and vinyl Index calculation

The effect of photo-oxidation was by monitoring of the IR absorbance of carbonyl and vinyl group of PE films using FTIR spectroscopy. Carbonyl index (CI) is defined as ratio of area under the absorbance of 1710 cm⁻¹ to the area under the reference peak at 1380 cm⁻¹, whereas vinyl index (VI) is the ratio of the area under the absorbance of vinyl group 909 cm⁻¹ to the area under the same reference peak (Ali et al. 2017). The carbonyl and vinyl indices were determined using the ratios as given below:

$$CI = \frac{A(1710)}{A(1380)}$$

$$VI = \frac{A(909)}{A(1380)}$$

Results and Discussion

This chapter has been divided into two sections to fulfill the overall goal of degrading microplastics in water. The first section describes the results obtained from MB degradation using modified photocatalysts. PE and its degradation mechanisms are discussed in the latter section.

Section A: Degradation of MB using Pt supported ZnO NRs

Different photocatalysts were prepared and its optical properties were also examined through UV-VIS and fluorescence spectroscopy. SEM images provided the surface information of the catalysts. In addition, ISO MB degradation test was conducted for evaluating the efficiency of photocatalytic agents and their degradation kinetics and its mechanism were discussed in the end.

Figure 17: SEM images of the top view demonstrate diameter and density of the prepared different concentration of ZnO NRs on glass substrate prepared by hydrothermal synthesis process. Also, side view shows the length of NRs. a) 3mM_5hrs, b) 5mM_5hrs.

Characterization of ZnO and deposited NPs Pt on ZnO NRs using SEM

ZnO NRs were grown on glass substrate using hydrothermal method (Barua and Dutta 2009). The morphology and elemental compositions of ZnO NRs and Pt coated ZnO NRs of different concentration were studied by SEM and EDX (Fig. 17 and 18, and Table 5). The average diameters

of the prepared ZnO NRs were observed as 25 nm, 35 nm, 45 nm, and 60 nm when grown for 5 hours duration with precursors of 3 mM, 5 mM, 10 mM and 20 mM concentration respectively. The lengths were found within the range of 200 nm to 1500 nm depending on the concentration (Fig. 17 a-d). So, the higher the concentration, the thicker and longer will be the NRs. In other words, the effective surface area will be elevated.

Pt was deposited on prepared ZnO NRs by photochemical reduction method using UV-C light. A study of Al-Alawi et al. (2016) revealed smaller and homogeneous distribution of the platinum particles on ZnO NRs of 10mM_5hr concentration. The study of SEM confirmed the changes occurred on the surface. The tips of Pt-ZnO NRs (fig.18) have changed due to the presence of Pt. The prepared Pt-EtOH solution was acidic (pH 5.5) but ZnO starts dissolving at this pH since the optimum pH for the ZnO stability in aqueous media should be between pH 7-11 (Liu and Gao 2015). The pH was not adjusted as it would interfere with the formation process of Pt NPs. For this reason, Pt with 20 minutes coating dissolved some of ZnO NRs as shown in fig. 18(d).

Figure 18: SEM images of the top view showing deposited Pt Nps on prepared 5mM_5hrs ZnO NRs using different deposition times by using photochemical reduction method. a) Pt-ZnO (5 min coating), b) Pt-ZnO (10 min coating), c) Pt-ZnO (15min coating), and d) Pt-ZnO.

The Pt-ZnO samples have been further characterized by EDX. The atomic (%) and weight (%) in the table 5 provides a rough estimation of the relative abundance of the molecules. It can also be observed that the percentage of platinum increases with prolonged deposition time.

Table 5: Summary of the elemental composition from EDX.

	Pt-ZnO 5 min coated		Pt-ZnO 10 min coated		Pt-ZnO 15 min coated		Pt-ZnO 20 min coated	
Element	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %
O	17.49	46.72	24.07	57.76	21.98	52.27	18.75	50.39
Zn	80.95	52.93	69.88	41.05	66.12	44.78	63.93	45.04
Pt	1.56	0.34	6.05	1.19	11.9	2.95	17.32	4.56

Optical properties of the substrates

UV-Vis absorption property

Figure 19: Typical optical absorption spectrum of hydrothermally grown ZnO (5mM_5hr) and Pt coated on ZnO samples by using photochemical reduction method. As compare to ZnO, Pt-ZnO samples show enhanced visible light absorption and suppression of UV region.

Optical absorption of the prepared samples of ZnO and Pt-ZnO was studied by UV-VIS spectroscopy over a range of 300 to 750 nm (Fig. 19). The absorption peaks of uncoated and platinum coated of Pt-ZnO (5 min coating), Pt-ZnO (10 min coating), Pt-ZnO (15min coating), and Pt-ZnO (20 min coating) are shown in fig. 19.

Upon platinum deposition, we observe an increased optical absorption in the visible region that can be attributed to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) absorption. A slight reduction of the absorption in the UV region could be due to blocking of UV portion of light from absorption by the metal clusters deposited on top of ZnO NRs,

Metal deposition curtails the penetrating ability of the photons by possibly scattering it which has a tendency to travel around the ZnO as the process modifies only the optical pathway of the photons (Michael et al. 2014). Overall, this phenomenon might be responsible for the reduction in intensity of band gap absorption. For platinum, surface plasmon oscillations peak is observed at 385 nm. Together with the scattered energy from ZnO by deposited NPs and SPR of platinum lead to change in the optical properties of the semiconductor and enhanced the visible light absorption (Lin et al. 2006). A small quantity of platinum deposition doubled the visible light absorption (at 400nm) than normal ZnO which has been particularly observed in the fig. 19.

Photoluminescence (PL) property

PL spectroscopy was used to observe the change in the emission spectra of both ZnO and Pt-ZnO deposited for 10 minutes. Photo excitation triggers the electrons to travel to the excited states and PL spectroscopy detects the energy released by these electrons once these return to their ground state. The quantity of the intensity is directly related to the rate of recombination and the wavelength of emission defines the energy states of the electronic defects.

Figure 20: Room temperature PL spectra of synthesized ZnO (5mM_5hr) NRs and Pt coated for 10 minutes on ZnO NRs with an excitation wavelength of 320 nm.

Room temperature PL spectra of synthesized ZnO (5mM_5hr) NRs and Pt coated for 10 minutes on ZnO NRs with an excitation wavelength 320 nm are shown in fig. 20. An excitation wavelength upto 345nm provides well established UV and visible emission states (Baral et al. 2017). It can be observed that PL intensity is considerably reduced by the loading of platinum on ZnO NRs which is expected due to the easy movement of electrons from semiconductor to the metal. It has been shown by several authors that platinum can form Schottky barrier in the junction with ZnO whereby backflow of schottky barrier electrons cannot occur to the semiconductor. Therefore, upon adding Pt to ZnO the recombination processes are lowered leading to lower intensity of the emission from defects (Zhang et al. 2005).

The study of Baral, et al. (2017) also categorized the emission band of ZnO into two parts: near band emission (NBE) and deep level emission (DLE). NBE ($\lambda < 400$ nm) band attributes to the UV emission region close to the ZnO band gap at 363 nm whereas DLE band is responsible for visible light emission. The defects in ZnO are solely responsible for DLE due to the recombination of photo-generated electrons with hole pairs (exactions).

Figure 21: Deconvoluted PL spectrum of ZnO NRs at excitation wavelength of 320 nm. I) Peak 1 at 406 nm II) Peak 2 at 444 nm III) Peak 3 at 463 nm IV) Peak 4 at 487 nm V) Peak 5 at 531 nm.

Fig. 21 and 22 show the deconvoluted PL spectra fitted using Gaussian function for ZnO and Pt-ZnO catalysts. No distinctive peaks at NBE region were found in both the cases due to the higher density of intrinsic or extrinsic defects. The selected five peaks from DLE band correspond to specific defect and color emission (Bora et al. 2017). The peak at 406 nm is due to electron transition from conduction band to the zinc vacancy (V_{Zn}) located at 0.3 eV from valence band (Jeong et al. 2003). Deep level zinc interstitial defects can be found in the region of 419 – 461 nm that are responsible for violet emission (Ahn et al. 2009). The second peak identified at 444 nm is attributed to electron transfer from zinc interstitial (Zn_i^{++}) donor defects to valence band. Doubly charged zinc interstitial

(Zn_i^{2+}) donor defect is located at Peak 3 at 463 nm. A peak at 487 nm can be attributed to the recombination of shallow trapped electron with acceptor level at 0.8 eV from valence band (Baral et al. 2017). A broad peak at 531 nm corresponds to singly ionized oxygen vacancy (V_o^+).

Figure 22: Deconvoluted PL spectrum of Pt coated for 10 minutes on ZnO NRs at excitation wavelength of 320 nm. I) Peak 1 at 406 nm II) Peak 2 at 444 nm III) Peak 3 at 463 nm IV) Peak 4 at 487 nm V) Peak 5 at 531 nm.

To evaluate the changes within selected peaks of ZnO and Pt-ZnO, relative intensities have been calculated by taking ratio of area under the higher peak to area to the corresponding peak. The intensities have been significantly reduced to 64% 63%, 83% and 49% for 406 nm, 444 nm, 463, 487 nm, and 531 nm respectively due to lower recombination of electrons. This is because electrons in the ZnO are transferred to the Pt for the balancing out the fermi levels to form Pt-ZnO junction and then get trapped due to schottky barrier formation.

Table 6: Relative intensities of selected peaks from PL spectra of ZnO (5mM_5hr) and Pt (10min coating)-ZnO substrates.

Peak	wavelength (nm)	Defects state	ZnO (5mM_5hr)	Pt (10min coating)-ZnO
			relative intensity	
I	406	V_{Zn}	1	1
II	444	Zn_i^{1+}	0.443622	0.1597
III	463	Zn_i^{2+}	0.082549	0.030045
IV	487	STe	0.26914	0.044887
V	531	V_o^+	0.089017	0.044907

Photocatalysis test

Initially, photocatalysis test was carried out using MB pollutant owing to its absorption peaks in the visible range to check the efficiency of the prepared catalysts. Prior to photodegradation, the photocatalyst surface was exposed to MB without illumination for reaching equilibrium absorption and desorption. The absorption peak of MB was found at 660 nm and its degradation with time using different catalytic agents was also observed visually for understanding the kinetics. The initial concentration was kept 10 μM for all through the study. Although the aim of this thesis is to use visible portion of EM spectrum, prepared catalysts (ZnO, Pt-ZnO) were exposed to both UV and VIS light for better comparisons.

Fig. 23 and 24 show the performance of both ZnO and platinum coated ZnO catalysts on MB degradation under both UV and VIS light where a mercury vapor lamp of 100 W power and a halogen lamp of intensity 70-80 klux were separately used as source. These tests were performed while keeping all the other parameters constant. MB was exposed for 90 minutes with and without catalysts and total five measurements were taken at 0, 20, 30, 45, and 90 minutes.

Figure 23: Percentage degradation of MB under UV irradiation using hydrothermally grown ZnO NRs (5 mM_5hr) and Pt coated on ZnO NRs with different deposition time (5, 10, 15, and 20 minute).

63% of MB was found to be degraded within 90 minute of UV light exposure using ZnO NRs while visible light irradiation reduced 38% of MB. The overall degradation rate was found low in comparison to UV as a result of wide bandgap of ZnO. The metal-oxide semiconductor is activated upon absorbing shorter wavelengths ($\lambda < 400$ nm) of the light spectra which are essential for generating OH^\cdot radicals that can oxidize MB which could be assigned as the reason behind the higher degradation (1.6 times higher for UV light irradiation). The formation of e^-h^+ pairs might be reduced when ZnO was exposed to visible light of longer wavelengths, $\lambda \geq 400$ nm. In such cases, only the tail

states (electronic defects) of ZnO was activated and participated in the redox process. Degradation of MB was also examined without using any catalysts for both conditions in order to check the photolysis and 33% degradation upon UV light irradiation and 25% degradation upon UV light irradiation was obtained similar to results reported in other studies (e.g. Anandan et al. 2007).

Figure 24: Percentage degradation of MB under VIS light irradiation using hydrothermally grown ZnO NRs (5 mM_5hr) and Pt coated on ZnO NRs with different deposition time (5, 10, 15, and 20 minute).

Upon coating the ZnO NRs with platinum nanoparticles (fig. 23 and 24), it was found that for samples prepared with 5 or 10 mins of platinum growth, the photodegradation increased with number of particles attached on the nanorods from 13% and 38% under UV irradiation; 3% and 16.5% respectively under visible light irradiation. However, upon deposition of platinum for longer periods, the photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue was found to decrease by 16% and 51% (under UV irradiation; 8% and 19% under visible light irradiation) for samples prepared with 15 and 20 minutes of deposition.

The improvement of photocatalytic efficiency for Pt-ZnO (5 min coating) and Pt-ZnO (10 min coating) and its subsequent reduction for higher platinum concentrations can be explained by considering the electron transfer mechanisms during photocatalysis process. The generated electrons (in electron-hole pairs) would move very easily to the metal surfaces due to the position of the bands, while the oxides of platinum formed at the ZnO interface will not allow any back-flow of electrons into ZnO nanorods, thus essentially separating the electron-hole pairs to carry out the oxidation and reduction processes. The holes participate in the formation of OH^\cdot radicals in presence of water causing oxidation of the MB. Also, the visible region was also activated owing to surface plasmon resonance (SPR) absorption (for platinum, typically at 385 nm). Both effects facilitate the redox reactions and reported to enhance photocatalysis (Wang et al. 2015).

The reduction in photocatalytic efficiency with higher concentration of Pt is an established knowledge. Driessen and Grassian (1998) observed that 0.1–2% Pt deposited on TiO₂ (Degussa P25) was detrimental for trichloroethene (TCE) photodegradation. Pt-NPs deposits (nanoparticles) blocks most of the active sites on the surface of ZnO nanorods leading to a reduction in e⁻-h⁺ pair generation. Also, A large amount of smaller sized metal deposited on semiconductor may increase the recombination process by reducing charge carrier space distance (CCSD) (Sadeghi et al. 1996).

Pt deposited on ZnO NRs for 10 minutes has been found to be most effective for MB degradation for both UV and VIS light irradiation. It can be observed from fig. 25 (a, b) that the degradation rate was higher at initial stage until 20 minute and then reduced gradually. This may be due to the reduction of colorless leuco-methylene blue into MB. The colour of MB changed from blue to almost colourless for UV and to light blue for VIS which can be confirmed by the reduction of absorption peak at 663 nm during the 90 minutes of photodegradation.

Figure 25: Optical absorptions showing photocatalytic degradation of MB using Pt coated ZnO NRs (10 minute) catalyst exposed to a) UV and b) VIS light irradiation for 90 minute.

The degradation process has been fitted to a pseudo first order kinetics by plotting $\log(C_t/C_0)$ vs time as shown on fig. 26 and 27. ZnO and Pt-ZnO catalysts in MB of 10 μ M concentration were exposed to both UV and VIS light separately. Pseudo first order slope represent the rate constant, k. As previously discussed, the highest photocatalytic efficiency was found for Pt-ZnO (10 min coating) sample followed by Pt-ZnO (5 min coating) and ZnO (5mM_5hr) for both cases.

The kinetic rate constant for ZnO, Pt-ZnO (5 min coating), Pt-ZnO (10 min coating), Pt-ZnO (15 min coating), and Pt-ZnO (20 min coating) were calculated to be 0.0049 min⁻¹, 0.0064 min⁻¹, 0.0102 min⁻¹, and 0.004 min⁻¹, and 0.0024 min⁻¹ respectively for UV light irradiation and 0.0034 min⁻¹, 0.0057 min⁻¹, 0.0062 min⁻¹, 0.0067 min⁻¹, 0.0052 min⁻¹, and 0.0046 min⁻¹ respectively when exposed to VIS light, as noted in the inset of the figures. Since, Pt-ZnO (10minute deposition) showed the best photocatalytic efficiency, it was selected for further studies on the degradation of LDPE.

Figure 26: Degradation kinetics of MB using ZnO (5mM_5hr) and Pt-ZnO catalysts exposed to UV light (power =100W) irradiation for 90 minute.

Figure 27: Degradation kinetics of MB using ZnO (5mM_5hr) and Pt supported ZnO catalysts exposed to VIS light irradiation for 90 minutes.

Proposed degradation mechanism

Upon photo-irradiation of semiconductors, light excites the electrons in the valence band to the conduction band wherein the electrons either get trapped in electronic defects leaving holes behind or can transfer to any adjoining materials with bands that are favorable for electron transfer imbuing photocatalysis. The band gap of ZnO is such that electron hole pairs can mainly be triggered by UV light illumination, whereas tail state defects just below the conduction band allows electron transitions by visible portion of the light. The generated electrons and holes lead to redox environment where hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), hydrogen ions (H^+) and superoxide ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) anions are generated due to the presence of water, air or dissolved oxygen (Qi et al. 2017; Baruah et al. 2010; Baruah et al. 2012). The degradation efficiency mainly depends on the number of holes generated by photons as discussed earlier which oxidizes the MB into colorless luco-methylene blue.

Figure 28: Energy band diagram of the Pt–ZnO junction before and after equilibrium; bandgap energy of ZnO = 3.4 eV, electron affinity of ZnO = 4.27 eV, and work function of Pt = 6.1 eV (Ghosh et al. 2012, Na et al. 2015). The energy band diagram is not drawn to actual scale.

The initial purpose of the study was to design a photocatalyst in a way that can perform both oxidation and reduction of pollutants, slow down the generation-recombination (RG) rates and utilize visible light of the solar spectrum; thereby, enhance the efficiency of the photocatalysis at a considerable extent. Therefore, platinum NPs have been deposited on ZnO surfaces to improve the efficiency by trapping the photogenerated electrons in the platinum which would lead to a higher number of holes. Photocatalytic degradation mechanism using plasmonic catalyst has been proposed based on the experiments made on MB pollutants. Two possible phenomena might be responsible for the observed catalytic conversion improvement: Schottky barrier formation and Surface Plasmonic Resonance (SPR). Although the mechanism of Schottky barrier in photocatalytic activity is well established but the influence of SPR stills remains inconsistent (Khan et al. 2015). Fig. 29 illustrates the proposed mechanism of enhancing photocatalytic activities of Pt-ZnO.

Figure 29: Possible mechanism of photocatalysis of MB when exposed to UV and VIS light using Pt coated ZnO photocatalyst.

When platinum is deposited on ZnO, the electrons from ZnO starts flowing towards empty energy state above fermi level of Pt until it reaches to equilibrium condition (fig. 28) as fermi level is lower for Pt than ZnO. At the interface of Pt-ZnO, it creates an energy barrier called schottky barrier which blocks the movement of electrons back to ZnO. The difference between work function and the electron affinity is the potential for SB. Pt has a work function of 6.1 eV, whereas n type ZnO (which is the case due to the non-stoichiometry in our materials) has an electron affinity of 4.27 eV. So, the electrons require higher than 1.83 eV energy to cross the junction (Na et al 2015). Therefore, Pt acts as an electron sink as a result of SB formation and increases the positively charged holes on the ZnO. These holes increase the production of hydroxyl radical (OH^-) compared to ZnO alone, thus enhancing the photocatalytic activity.

While Schottky barriers enhance the photo activity by trapping the electron, surface plasmon resonance (SPR) can also trap the electrons within its electrical field cloud. This can also generate positive charge at alternate surface of the metal. At specific wavelength, electrons start oscillating at the interface of Pt-ZnO interface; creating a localized electron field due to collective oscillation of

those electrons. The electron density increases at one part whereas decreases in the other part. This process of oscillation and electric field creation is called localized surface plasmon resonance (SPR). The SPR level is at 385 nm which is the reason given for higher degradation efficiency of MB under UV light irradiation (Lin et al. 2006; Khan et al. 2015).

The deposition of Pt NPs on ZnO NRs has been found to be a successful way to suppress electron-hole recombination which in turn increased the number of holes for the photocatalytic reactions. Owing to fermi level equilibrium, the transferred electrons from the ZnO were trapped within the empty energy level of the Pt due to SB which slows down the e-h⁺ recombination process as evidenced by Dong et al. (2017). Also, there might be additional hole generation other than ZnO at the fermi level of platinum due to SPR. Further, visible light absorption increases by about 50% (Fig. 19) due to SPR absorption. All of these phenomena lead to higher efficiency in photogenerated charge separation and improvement of visible light absorption ultimately leading to higher photocatalysis which has been represented in the fig. 29.

In order to justify the suggested mechanism, especially to confirm whether the number of positively charged h⁺ has increased or not and to identify the main reactive species from *OH⁻ and O₂⁻ radicals, the photodegradation of MB was performed in presence of Isopropanol which acts as a *OH⁻ sucker (Vinoth et al. 2017).

Figure 30: Effect of 20 μM ISP on degradation kinetics of MB using ZnO and Pt-ZnO under VIS light. The test has been conducted with and without mixing ISP.

Fig. 30 shows significant change in degradation kinetics once ISP was mixed in the MB solution during the photocatalytic degradation studies. The degradation kinetics of Pt-ZnO (10min coating) catalyst reduced dramatically from 0.0134 min^{-1} to 0.0074 min^{-1} when ISP was added in MB solution. A reduction of photocatalytic degradation rate from 0.0114 min^{-1} to 0.0087 min^{-1} was observed for

ZnO. ISP has an affinity towards $h^+/*OH^-$ radical that can be reduced to $(CH_3)_2C^*(OH)$ radicals (lyunt et al. 2016). So, instead of oxidation of the MB, ISP scavenge the $*OH^-$ radicals that lead to the reduction of overall photodegradation. Thus $*OH^-$ radicals are the most reactive species for the degradation of MB dye pollutant. Higher photocatalytic efficiency of 17.5% was observed for Pt – ZnO (10 min coating) substrate in comparison to ZnO alone. This imparts an evidence of the increased number of holes in the reaction system. However, the result is better compared to the first tests reported in fig. 24. This may be due to reuse of same catalysts for both UV and VIS studies.

Section B: Photocatalytic degradation of PE using designed catalysts

This section describes the results obtained from photo-oxidative degradation of PE using previously optimized photocatalysts. The solid-state LDPE samples along with designed catalysts were kept in water and exposed to VIS light irradiation for 175 hours.

The changes within the molecular level of LDPE were primarily monitored using FTIR spectroscopy. Morphological and visco elastic changes were also observed through optical microscope, SEM and DMA respectively. Finally, the degradation mechanism of PE has been proposed based on the results obtained in the study.

Morphological result of LDPE

Microscopic result

Changes in surface morphology due to photocatalytic exposure PE was initially studied with an optical microscope (fig. 31: a-f). All the images were captured using 500 μ m scale. The effect of ZnO catalysts synthesized with different reactant concentrations (3mM_5hr, 10mM_5hr, 20mM_5hr) and plasmonic catalyst of Pt-ZnO (10mins coating-10mM_5mM) on PE samples were explored individually. Images of as received LDPE and photo-irradiated LDPE without catalysts were also examined for better comparison.

It is to be mentioned that as received LDPE samples have some internal defects that might have occurred during manufacturing process. The radicals formed by the designed semiconductor photocatalyst always start attacking on these weak spots (inherent defects) first including chromophoric groups and then gradually penetrate deeper into the samples. The longer and thicker are the NRs of ZnO, the higher is the degradation of PE as proved by the textural changes on the surface Pt-ZnO catalyst caused most damages to LDPE film due to higher degradation efficiency as proved in the MB degradation study, which is due to the higher available surface area.

Figure 31: Microscopic images of a) Pure LDPE b) LDPE after 175hrs exposure without catalyst c) LDPE after 175hrs exposure using ZnO (3mM-5hr.) d) LDPE after 175hrs exposure using ZnO (10mM-5hr.) e) LDPE after 175hrs exposure using ZnO (20mM-5hr.) f) LDPE after.

SEM result

SEM was also used for better perceptibility of topographical changes in nanometer scale that could not be detected in the microscope. Fig. 32 (c-d) shows the images taken using SEM for LDPE composites after visible light exposure for 175 hours. The surface of the pure LDPE was found smooth and had no visible cracks as compared to others (fig. 32a). Few cracks and small holes of sizes less than 2-4 μm were formed on PE sample that was exposed to white light without any catalyst (Fig. 32b).

Figure 32: SEM images of a) Pure LDPE b) LDPE after 175hrs exposure without catalyst c) LDPE after 175hrs exposure using ZnO (10mM-5hr.) d) LDPE after 175hrs exposure using Pt-ZnO (10 min coating-10mM-5hr).

Several wrinkles and cavities, with varying sizes of 10 μ m or less, were detected all over the surface of the LDPE sample following photocatalytic degradation using plasmonic catalyst in comparison to ZnO (10mM_5hr) alone for the same duration of light irradiation. These holes occur due to the formation of volatile compounds inside LDPE during photocatalytic degradation which are removed from the polymer matrices (Li et al. 2008). This result demonstrates the better performance of plasmonic catalysts than ZnO alone for PE degradation as well.

Changes in the chemical properties of LDPE

The most popular, nondestructive, and time saving analytical technique for analyzing the degradation of polymer is using FTIR spectroscopy which provides a reasonable but indirect measurement of the extent of oxidation. Polymeric compounds absorb light at different wavenumbers as each functional group vibrates at its own characteristic frequency, some of which are shown in fig. 33, 34, and 35.

Fig. 33 shows characteristic spectrum of LDPE in FTIR before irradiation where nine strongly vibrated peaks were found within the region of 600 - 750 cm^{-1} , 1350 - 1480 cm^{-1} , and 2850 - 2975 cm^{-1} . These absorptions belong to different functional groups that vibrate at different modes and intensity. Medium type rocking deformation of CH_2 was observed to occur at 710 cm^{-1} , and 719 cm^{-1} , which are important for the characterization of PE (Ali et al. 2017). It has also been found that CH_2 bond exhibits strong stretching vibrations below 3000 cm^{-1} , whilst their asymmetric stretching vibration occurs at 2915 cm^{-1} and symmetric stretching at 2847 cm^{-1} (Gulmine et al. 2002). LDPE has higher branching of monomer than HDPE which is characterized by the presence of the methyl (CH_3 -) group. It absorbs frequencies within the region of 1385-1370 cm^{-1} and shows weak symmetric deformation of the bond. A strong carbon-carbon double bonds started stretching at 1462 cm^{-1} and 1472 cm^{-1} , can be seen in the figure 4.16 (Socrates 2001). Table 4 (see appendix) shows the summary of the groups found in the FTIR spectra of LDPE.

Figure 33: FTIR spectra of pure LDPE film before irradiation.

During photocatalytic degradation, the PE undergoes several chemical transformations that results in gradual embrittlement of the molecules with time and exposure. Several new functional groups like carbonyl, hyperoxide, peroxide, and unsaturated bonds are observed in fig. 34. The effect of ZnO (10nmM_5hrs) photocatalyst on PE degradation was monitored initially at a regular interval through FTIR spectroscopy.

Fig. 36 shows formation of carbonyl groups within the range of 1700-1760 cm^{-1} . The peaks observed at 1708 cm^{-1} , 1719 cm^{-1} , 1738 cm^{-1} and 1747 cm^{-1} can be assigned to carboxylic acid, ketones, aldehyde and esters respectively (Ali, S. et al. 2017). The peaks are fairly broad and clearly observed in the spectra after 175 hours exposure. Initially, ester and aldehyde were obscured and then revealed their individual peaks after 50 hours of irradiation. This may be due to the delay in generation of carboxylic acid and hydroperoxides as the formation of ester imitated by these groups.

Figure 34: FTIR transmittance spectra of LDPE-ZnO composite film during visible light exposure of 175 hours. LDPE sample was kept in contact with ZnO (10mM_5hr) catalyst.

Figure 35: FTIR absorbance spectra of LDPE-ZnO composite film after visible light exposure of different time intervals.

Figure 36: FTIR absorbance spectra of carbonyl group (1675-1800 cm^{-1}) during photocatalytic degradation of LDPE-ZnO composite using visible light..

Figure 37: Generation of unsaturated groups due to photocatalytic degradation of LDPE-ZnO film after visible light exposure at different time intervals.

Photocatalysis of ketones resulted in formation of unsaturated groups: Vinylidene ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CR}_2$) and vinyl ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHR}$) and a chain end ketone, which were detected at 888 cm^{-1} and 909 cm^{-1} as suggested by Gardette, M. et al (2013). The reactions that are involved in the process can be termed as Norrish type II. Fig. 37 indicates the formation of two unsaturated groups and their changes in the absorbance during photo-excitation of ZnO-PE nanocomposites.

The formation of alcohol species like hydroxyl groups was confirmed by the weak stretching within the range 3450 - 3650 cm^{-1} wavenumbers, which did not change significantly during this experiment. The narrow and weak peak at 3563- 3548 cm^{-1} is due to hydrogen-bonded hydroperoxides whereas the broad absorbance peak at 3592- 3519 cm^{-1} can be attributed to non-hydrogen bonded alcohols (Fig. 38), which were also reported by Kumayanka, (2010).

Figure 38: Generation of hydroperoxide groups (3450-3700 cm^{-1}) after visible light exposure of LDPE-ZnO composite at different time intervals.

Figure 39: Generation of peroxide groups (1000-1350 cm^{-1}) when PE-ZnO nanocomposite was exposed to VIS light irradiation for 175 hours.

The absorbance intensity is usually complex within the range of 1000-1350 cm^{-1} that belongs to peroxides (C-O) group. Photocatalytic degradation of PE also generated some peroxide groups in presence of oxygen. These oxygenated products are indicated by the broad adsorption in this region. Three detectible peroxide groups were found in the FTIR spectra (fig. 39). A broad visible peak between 1280-1325 cm^{-1} that can be assigned to secondary peroxide and a peak at 1170 cm^{-1} from primary peroxide groups. Another sharp peak between 1040-1055 cm^{-1} could be from unsaturated peroxide groups (Socrates 2001). A summary of both generated and transformed functional groups on visible light irradiation of PE-ZnO nanocomposite are summarized in table 7.

Table 7: Observed functional groups in PE-ZnO nanocomposite film following solar light irradiation for 175 hours.

	Bonding	Type of vibration	intensity	Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
After irradiation	-C=C-	Out of plane deformation	Strong	908
	-C=C-	Out of plane deformation	strong	888
	-C-O	stretching	Medium strong	1050, 1170
	>C=O	Stretching	Very strong	1708, 1719, 1738, 1747
	-OH	stretching	Variable	3558, 3606

A most commonly used indicator of monitoring chemical oxidation of PE is the carbonyl index (CI). Effects of different photocatalysts on oxidative degradation of LDPE were examined by plotting CI as a function of exposure time. Fig. 40 illustrates of CI and VI of LDPE and its composites due to photocatalytic irradiation. It can be observed that the degree of degradation (CI) increased with exposure time and varied when different types of catalysts were used. The slope of the CI plots implies that oxidation is occurring rapidly by using designed catalysts. Higher formation of carbonyl groups determines the higher degradation of PE.

Figure 40: a) Carbonyl index (CI) and b) Vinyl Index of pure LDPE and nano composites.

The initial CI value of pure LDPE was found to be 0.71 and the value changes slightly when exposed to visible light without any catalyst. The default value ensures the presence of inherent chromophore of the PE sample. PE can disintegrate on continuous exposure to solar radiation, especially by UV light, as the molecules become activated by absorbing the light and start weathering in presence of oxygen. Catalyst can greatly expedite the oxidation process as observed in the above figure. The CI values were found to be 1.61 and 1.38 for irradiated PE samples in the presence of Pt-ZnO (10min coating-10mM_5hr) and ZnO (10mM_5hr) respectively. An increment of 16% in the formation of carbonyl groups within PE was found by using plasmonic photocatalyst due to higher OH⁻ radical production during photoexcitation since this is the main constituent for the breakdown of PE as suggested in the studies of Ali et al (2016). It can be also observed from the graph that, CI value increases with the increase in catalysts concentration because of the presence of thicker, longer and denser NRs.

In addition to CI, the degree of PE degradation was also indirectly detected by the formation of unsaturated groups like vinyl and vinylidene. It has been mentioned earlier that the unsaturated groups are generated as a part of Norrish type II reaction from ketone which implies oxidation of PE. Fig. 40b shows variation of VI of visible light exposed LDPE samples and its composites as a function of time and catalysts. Vinyl groups has been observed to form linearly as a result of chain branching of LDPE-ZnO composite samples.

Changes in the mechanical properties of LDPE

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was performed to observe the effect of photocatalytic degradation on viscoelastic properties, which combine the characteristics of elastic solids and Newtonian fluids, of LDPE. Samples were exposed to dynamic loads at different temperatures ranges varying from -20 to 70°C by maintaining a constant sinusoidal frequency. Fig. 42 shows the variations in storage modulus (E) of pure and visible light irradiated LDPE samples in presence of ZnO NRs of different concentrations at different temperatures during measurement. LDPE samples were irradiated under visible light in presence of ZnO (3mM_5hr), ZnO (10mM_5hr), and ZnO (20mM_5hr) catalysts.

Figure 41: Variation in the visco-elastic properties of pure and irradiated LDPE after 175 hours of exposure. a) pink: Pure LDPE, b) yellow: LDPE-ZnO (3mM_5hr), and c) blue: LDPE-ZnO (10mM_5hr).

LDPE is semi-crystalline in nature and start developing toughness when exposed to visible light active catalysts. For this reason, the storage modulus was found to be higher for exposed samples. Therefore, higher value of the storage modulus (E) indicates stiffer and brittle condition of the samples. DMA result suggests that the exposed films lost its elasticity following the photocatalytic treatment. Loss of elasticity and very high increase in the modulus reveals that the photocatalytic exposure affects the films and higher is the concentration of ZnO NRs, higher is its influence, which is understandable since the reaction rate is faster in these photocatalysts attributed to the increased surface area.

Proposed polyethylene degradation mechanism

The degradation mechanism of pure LDPE without any catalyst has been extensively studied. Photon induced from the light source creates alkyl radicals, and then undergo other oxidation reactions as we have discussed above. Photocatalytic degradation of LDPE is different than photolytic degradation of pure LDPE.

It has been discussed in the previous section A that hydroxy (*OH) and superoxide (*O₂⁻) radicals generated in the presence of moisture during photoexcitation of the ZnO or Pt-ZnO catalysts formed when electrons got excited in the valence band by the absorption of photons induced due to visible light irradiation in the presence of a photocatalyst. Plasmonic catalysts generated comparatively higher amount of *OH⁻ radicals that enhanced the degradation of PE similar to what we have reported for the MB degradation.

The generated radicals initiated the degradation process followed by chain breaking, branching, crosslinking and oxidation of LDPE. The degradation mechanism of LDPE has been schematically illustrated in the fig. 42. At the onset of photodegradation process, alkyl chains, in direct contact with the photocatalysts, are attacked by the radicals. Alkyl radicals are formed by the abstraction of hydrogen inducing breakage of the polymer chain by forming hydroperoxides in presence of oxygen. Once alkoxy radicals are formed, they propagate within the polymer chain, leading to chain cleavage in the presence of oxygen and generate carbonyl and unsaturated groups which have been observed in the FTIR spectra during the degradation of PE.

Alkoxy radicals are the main interim species that produce aldehydes, ester, ketones and carboxylic acids in the Photooxidation process of LDPE in the presence of catalysts. Ketone is the key compound in saturated hydrocarbon which goes through further irradiation and results in the formation of radicals and vinyl groups (Ali et al. 2016; Shang et al. 2003; Gardette et al 2013).

The reactions that are involved in the photolysis or hemolysis of unsymmetrical ketones to form two radicals by α -cleavage of carbon and hydrogen abstraction are called Norrish type I reactions. These radicals can turn into carbon mono-oxides (Dinda 2018). Ketones may form chain end ketone and unsaturated groups (vinyl and vinylidene) through abstraction of γ hydrogen from long polymeric ketones, the reaction is well known as Norrish type II. In These carbonyl groups can be further oxidized to form volatile organic compounds like ethane, formaldehyde etc. (Shang et al. 2003) and can mineralize to CO₂ and H₂O.

Conclusion

The persistent nature of microplastics and their infinitesimal size with potential lethal consequences is being noticed by researchers and societies across the world and new means of degradation of these plastics to save the earth's environment from getting further polluted is the need of the hour. Thus, in this work, a major focus was on the analysis and development of the scientific principles and experimental techniques to accelerate the break-down of documented microplastic pollutants particularly LDPE through heterogeneous photocatalysis process using high surface area designer photocatalysts, namely zinc oxide nanorods (ZnO NRs) and platinum coated zinc oxide nanorods (Pt-ZnO NRs). The optical properties of ZnO were modified using metal (Pt-NPs) to improve the overall plasmonic photocatalysis performances by lowering down the recombination processes and improving the visible light absorbance for application of visible light photocatalysts using sunlight.

The morphological, elemental and optical characterization of both ZnO and Pt-ZnO catalysts were carried out using electron microscopy techniques (SEM, EDX) and optical spectroscopy (UV-VIS and photoluminescence). The growth of ZnO NRs and the deposition of Pt NPs on ZnO NRs both were followed by SEM and EDX, respectively. The secular UV-VIS absorption of the Pt-ZnO catalysts was low in the band gap region but high in visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum attributed to photon scattering (UV region) and surface plasmon resonance (SPR) (visible region) due to the presence of platinum NPs. Plasmonic (Pt) metal NPs. The results obtained from photoluminescence spectroscopy showed lower recombination of electrons in Pt-ZnO catalysts.

Standard protocol (ISP 10678: 2010) using MB dye pollutant was conducted for the assessment of photocatalytic performance of the synthesized ZnO NRs and Pt-ZnO NRs, upon excitation by both UV and VIS light sources. Since, only electronic defects of ZnO catalyst were activated upon visible light exposure, the overall degradation was found to be 0.625 times lower than under UV light irradiation. Size and number of the platinum nanoparticles deposited on the ZnO nanorods influenced the photocatalytic efficiency. 10 minutes deposition time for platinum nanoparticles growth was found to be optimum increasing the photodegradation by about 38% under UV irradiation and 16.5% under visible light. In Platinum nanoparticles deposited on ZnO, the fermi-level between metal-semiconductor adjusts for the electrons to move from the semiconductor to the metals efficiently, while the formation of schottky barrier at the interface reduces the backflow of electrons into the semiconductor for recombination, thus enhancing the oxidation of MB due to this efficient electron-hole pair separation. The contribution of the hydroxyl radicals to the photodegradation process was tested by introducing Isopropanol (IP) into the MB solution (IP are OH⁻ radicals scavengers). The degradation kinetics of MB was significantly reduced when the scavenger of OH radicals were introduced in the system.

50 μm commercial LDPE film was irradiated for 175 hours with visible light in the presence of photocatalysts (ZnO and Pt-ZnO). Changes in the properties of LDPE were observed through FTIR spectroscopy, DMA, and Optical microscope and SEM.

Formation of low molecular weights of various functional groups after photocatalytic degradation was observed; characteristic peaks within the range of 3600-3610 cm^{-1} , 1700-1760 cm^{-1} , 1100-1300 cm^{-1} , and 880-920 cm^{-1} revealed the formation of hydro-peroxides, peroxides, and unsaturated groups respectively in the FTIR spectra of LDPE film. The presence of higher CI indicated the higher degree of oxidation and indirectly confirming the disintegration of LDPE upon visible light exposure.

An early CI value before irradiation ensures the existence of chromophores; that are necessary to initiate photooxidative degradation process using catalysts that provide a favorable platform for efficient molecular interactions through formation of oxidizing agents (*OH· radicals). 19% increase in the oxidation rate was found by using plasmonic catalyst (Pt-ZnO) in comparison to ZnO (10mM_5hr). Vinyl index is also an indication of LDPE disintegration. The formation pattern of vinyl groups was almost similar to the carbonyl groups except the vinyl contents increased first, and then decreased as a function of time due to decrease in double bond compounds.

Optical microscope and SEM results showed that the mechanical damages in the polymer matrix occurred following photocatalytic degradation process. Enhanced wrinkles, cracks and cavities were observed in the LDPE sheets when photodegraded in the presence of plasmonic catalyst.

Elastic behavior of LDPE after irradiation was also observed through dynamic mechanical analyzer wherein the LDPE samples were found to be stiffer and brittle upon photodegradation in presence of the catalysts.

The results of the present work provide a new insight about using heterogenous photocatalysis for degradation of microplastic pollutants in water. The findings from this work will be helpful for handling MPs in wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) to control the undesirable entrance in the waterbodies.

Uncertainties

Errors and uncertainties can't be fully eliminated, was reduced through careful selection of parameters and experimental settings. To avoid any discrepancy and error in the results, at least three measurements were done while using different characterization tools.

Parameters like light intensity, bulb position, angle of exposure, pH, water level, initial dye concentration, volume, etc. were kept constant for all the tests made in the study. The efficiency for chemical transformation of pollutants mainly depends on light intensity and the catalyst substrates. Number of nanorods can influence the results at a great extent. Assumed uniform and homogenous NRs formation on all the glass substrates may not be true in all cases and can interfere in the results. As ZnO has a tendency of photo erosion and same Pt-ZnO were irradiated under UV and VIS light, the recycling may have resulted in low photocatalysis efficiency. Moreover, LDPE degradation should have been done in a more controlled environment to monitor the influences of other factors and consider them during analysis of the result.

Future scope

The present study investigated the effect of ZnO and modified ZnO NRs using Pt NPs on photocatalysis of low density polyethylene. One of the aims of the study was to use solar light for attaining energy efficiency. Degradation efficiency can be improved using other processes like depositing non-metals, transitional metals etc. Also, coupling with carbon materials may provide further enhancement in the charge separation efficiency. Breaking down of LDPE using designed catalysts produced several volatile compounds, CO, CO₂ and H₂O. Study through gas chromatograph (GC) or liquid chromatography (LC) would give a better understanding of photocatalytic degradation mechanism and to establish a relation in the degradation kinetics.

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Appendix

Part A: Tables

Table 1: Properties of ZnO semiconductor.

Properties	
Band gap (E_g)	3.2
Structure type	Wurtzite
Lattice constant	$c = 0.3296$ nm; $a = 0.52065$ nm; $c/a = 1.633$
Type of semiconductors	N type (mostly)
Density, d	5.606 g/cm ³
Color	white
Dielectric constant (ϵ)	8.75
Solubility (at 30°C)	Water soluble 1.6 mg L ⁻¹
Electron mobility (at room temperature)	200 cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Hole mobility (at room temperature)	$5-30$ cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Binding energy (eV)	60

Table 2: Different amounts of equimolar concentrations of hexamethylenetetramine and zinc nitrate hexahydrate in deionizer water forming the growth solutions-

Concentration of growth solution (equimolar)	Amount of hexamethylenetetramine (gm)	Amount of zinc nitrate hexahydrate (gm)	equimolar volume of solution (ml)
3 mM	0.21	0.446	500
5 mM	0.35	0.744	
10 mM	0.70	1.487	
20 mM	0.84	1.78	

Table 3: Determination of relative intensity of designed photocatalyst from PL spectroscopy analysis.

SL	ZnO (5mM_5hr)					Pt (10min coating)-ZnO (5mM_5hr)		
	wavelength of selected peak	energy of selected peak	Area under peak	height	relative intensity	Area under peak	height	relative intensity
1	406	3.05	615.203	23.86447	1	480.7673	8.87569	1
2	444	2.79	272.9179	6.51891	0.443622	76.7786	1.49368	0.1597
3	463	2.68	50.78455	30.49587	0.082549	14.44483	7.58596	0.030045
4	487	2.54	165.5759	13.26133	0.26914	21.58032	2.65984	0.044887
5	531	2.33	54.7636	3.39179	0.089017	21.58975	1.14248	0.044907

Table 4: Observed functional groups in unexposed LDPE film.

	Bonding	Type of vibration	intensity	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)
Before irradiation	-CH ₂	Bending	Medium	610, 618
	-CH ₂ -	Rocking deformation	medium	710,719
	-CH ₃	Symmetric deformation	weak	1377
	-C=C-	stretching	strong	1462, 1472
	-CH ₂ -	Asymmetric stretching	Strong	2915
	-CH ₂ -	Symmetric stretching	strong	2847

Part B: Pictures

Figure 1: Setup to perform seeding process for hydrothermal synthesis of ZnO NRs.

Figure 2: FTIR spectroscopy (Thermo scientific: Nicolet is10)

Figure 3: UV-VIS spectroscopy (PerkinElmer's LAMBDA-750 UV/Vis)

Figure 4: Florescence spectroscopy (PerkinElmer (LS 55))

Figure 5: Scanning electron microscope (FEG-SEM: Ultra 55, ZEISS)